

THREE-DIMENSIONAL FLOW SIMULATION OF RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING FOR COMPOSITE WHEEL RIM

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ABSTRACT

Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) is one of the most common process for manufacturing polymer composites. The prediction of flow front and filling time of polymer resin can be important factor in order to produce carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) rims which have either simple or complex shape. However, it is hard to predict the resin flow accurately which passes through the multilayer fabric preform with different patterns. Therefore, we suggest a three dimensional numerical model to investigate the resin flow behavior in complicated structure during the RTM process. The 3D numerical simulation is performed by using permeability tensors of different fabrics. Based on the results of numerical analysis, the process optimization for RTM will be possible by controlling diverse variables.

1 INTRODUCTION

RTM is a manufacturing process that uses a liquid resin to saturate a fiber preform placed in a closed mold cavity. It has great potential to produce complex polymer composite structures with good surface and uniform quality. In order to reduce expensive trial and error, the prediction of resin flow behavior and void formation are necessary for optimizing various process parameters and conditions.^[1,2]

In this study, we suggest a three dimensional (3D) numerical model to investigate the resin flow behavior in a complicated mold for fabricating Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) rims. The effect of fabric structures on the filling pattern and the void formation is examined by comparing two cases.

2 THEORY AND MODELING

2.1 Theory

To solve the 3D RTM problem, the PAM-RTM[®] software which is a commercial simulation program based on the finite element method (FEM) was used. In this numerical analysis, the resin is impregnated into the fabric preform considered as a porous medium. The resin flow which is treated as a Newtonian flow is governed by Darcy's law (Eq.1) combined with continuity equation (Eq.2). The pressure gradient and the velocity field were obtained by solving the combined equation.

Darcy's law:

$$\mathbf{u} = \frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} \cdot \nabla P \quad (1)$$

Continuity equation:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (2)$$

The macro/micro-voids formation is related to flow velocity and flow front of resin. At low flow velocity, macro-voids tend to be generated more easily, whereas high fluid velocity leads to micro-voids formation. The functions of macro- and micro-voids content are as follows.^[3,4]

Macro-voids function:

$$-1574 \cdot v + 12.82 \quad (3)$$

Micro-voids function:

$$100.5 \cdot v + 1.27 \quad (4)$$

2.2 Modeling

The geometrical structure of CFRP rim with mold trap is shown in Fig. 1a. The three dimensional model was composed of the preform parts (part A and B, green and blue region) and the trap part (part C, red region). Two different laminated structures were investigated for the preform parts. One structure consisted of two different non-crimp fabrics, and the other structure consisted of twill fabrics and unidirectional (UD) fabrics. Therefore, different permeability values which we obtained in the experiment were used for each fabric.

For the boundary condition, the constant inlet pressure along the out-of-plane direction was imposed. Each location of three inlet gates and outlet vents were marked by navy and yellow arrows respectively in Fig. 1a.

Figure 1: (a) Geometry with 3 inlet gates and vents, (b) the cross-section of CFRP rim with mold trap.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The RTM process was simulated for two different preform structures as mentioned above to study the effect of fabric structures on the resin flow behavior and the final property of the composite rim.

3.1 NCF $\pm 45^\circ$ & 0° fabrics

Fig. 2 shows the results of the filling factor and the content of macro-voids for the NCF fabrics case. The resin was impregnated into the trap part firstly in several seconds, and then filled equivalently along the positive z direction. The predicted total filling time of the polymer resin was about 823 s and most of the detected macro-voids were distributed at the complex curved part of the model.

Figure 2: (a) Overall and (b) the magnified cross-section view of the flow front (when $t = 39$ s), (c) overall and (d) the magnified cross-section view of macro-voids content (when 100% filling).

3.2 Twill & UD fabrics

The results of the resin flow behavior are illustrated in Fig.3. In the cross-section view, the filling pattern is quite different with the results of the previous case, which is contributed to the different permeability values of the fabrics. Moreover, the total filling time was reduced to about 516 s and the detected macro-voids were mainly formed on the top of the geometry.

Figure 3: (a) Overall and (b) the magnified cross-section view of the flow front (when $t = 42$ s), (c) overall and (d) the magnified cross-section view of macro-voids content (when 100% filling).

4 CONCLUSION

We suggested the 3D numerical simulation to predict the resin flow behavior in the mold during the RTM process with respect to the effect of different fabric structures. Compared with the NCF case, the twill and UD case showed less macro-void content and shorter filling time. Therefore, we may select appropriate fabric structures and lay-up configuration to minimize the void formation and enhance the property of CFRP composite rim.

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REFERENCES

- [1] L.A. Isoldi, C.P. Oliveira, L.A. Rocha, J.A. Souza, S.C. Amico, Three-dimensional numerical modeling of RTM and LRTM processes, *Journal of the Brazilian Society of Mechanical Sciences and Engineering*, **34**(2), 2012, pp. 105-111.
- [2] J.A. Garcia-Manrique, R. Hoto, L. Gascon, J. Andres, A numerical simulation of woven/anionic polyamide 6 composite part manufacturing using structural reactive injection moulding process, *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, **29**(2), 2016, pp. 219-233.
- [3] E. Poodts, G. Minak, L. Mazzocchetti, L. Giorgini, Fabrication, process simulation and testing of a thick CFRP component using the RTM process, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **56**, 2014, pp. 673-680.
- [4] E. Ruiz, V. Achim, S. Soukane, F. Trochu, J. Breard, Optimization of injection flow rate to minimize micro/macro-voids formation in resin transfer molded composites, *Composites science and technology*, **66**(3), 2006, pp. 475-486.